

Case report: Dapagliflozin, a glucosuria-inducing treatment in diabetic adult on a very low carbohydrate diet

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Abstract

Gliflozins are synthetic glucose transporter inhibitors and have a blood glucose lowering effect independent of any insulin effect. They induce glucosuria by inhibiting glucose reabsorption from the urine volume.

Case: A 58 year old white male, 4 years since diabetes diagnosis and on a <50 g per day carbohydrate restricted diet to manage serum glucose. Dapagliflozin 5 mg/day was introduced over a nearly 5-month period.

As expected, serum glucose was reduced through induced glucosuria by 1-1.5 mmol/L. Other expected effects were polyuria and polydipsia, associated with awakening 4-6 times per night. Some loss of weight was recorded, but whether this relates to glucose loss or the near-diarrhoeal intestinal side effect is difficult to determine. Shortly after commencing treatment, a serum lipid test was conducted indicating dyslipidaemia and insulin resistance. A further serum lipid test following a two week cessation of Dapagliflozin near the middle of the 5 month treatment period resulted in a reversion to a lipids profile prior to treatment.

The glucagon stimulation by gliflozins was noted as an increased fasting glucose concentration from approximately 8-10 mmol/L to 12-16 mmol/L before and after treatment. It is unknown whether this would be self-correcting as Glipizide, and subsequently insulin, treatment commenced. Although glucagon stimulation has been suggested to occur via SGLT2 inhibition of pancreatic α -cells, the presence of SGLT2 here is disputed. However, gastrointestinal α -cells could be the glucagon source associated with SGLT1 inhibition.

Introduction

A new treatment option based on induced glucosuria shows promise towards managing diabetic hyperglycaemia.^{4,11,38} Although glucosuria, with associated polyuria and polydipsia, has long been recognised as a symptom of diabetes,^{12,13} this new treatment option specifically targets glucose transporters at the point where filtered glucose is recovered from the urine volume. This therapy has also been proposed as likely to help preserve β -cell mass.²⁶

Induced glucosuria as a therapy for diabetes has resulted in increased interest in renal glucose transport and inhibition. A number of reviews contribute to understanding the therapy and modes of action.^{9,12,36} Two isoforms of sodium glucose co-transporter (SGLT1 and SGLT2) provide glucose transport against a concentration gradient.³⁹ Under normal conditions, the kidneys are recognised to filter about 180g glucose per day, of which about 97% is reabsorbed via SGLT2 and the remaining 3% via SGLT1 transporters, leaving only a trace of glucose lost via urination. With some variation in individuals, this functions well until serum glucose rises to 10-12 mmol/L, at which time the excess fails to be reabsorbed and glucosuria begins. Under persistent hyperglycaemic conditions, this threshold typically increases to 12-14 mmol/L, thus exacerbating hyperglycaemia of diabetes. SGLT2 inhibitors prevent reabsorption via this class of glucose transporter and thus glucosuria develops,

however applying inhibition to SGLT2 transporters results in only 30-50% loss of glucose rather than the expected 90+%.⁷

Elevating renal glucose excretion reduces plasma glucose independent of any insulin effect. In 2013, the first of the gliflozin drugs, also called SGLT2 inhibitors, was registered for clinical use.²² The anti-glycaemic action is therefore loss of serum glucose via urine. In addition to glucosuria, weight loss is a common beneficial side effect. Polydipsia and polyuria are reported, as well as mild reduction in hypertension. Dyslipidaemia, especially an increase in LDL cholesterol^{3,11,14,19} and increased gluconeogenesis²¹ are noted. An increase in urogenital yeast infections is reasonably common.⁸ Less common are the few cases of euglycaemic ketoacidosis,¹ and very recently also a few cases of necrotising fasciitis.³⁵ SGLT2-inhibition also stimulates glucagon production,^{10,212,10,21,24,29} commonly considered an anti-hypoglycaemic benefit via enhanced endogenous glucose release. Improved kidney function has also been reported.³⁶

Although the prime focus of this class of drug is on its serum glucose lowering effect, these other effects indicate a broader activity, presumably resulting from adaptations to loss of SGLT2 function.

Case

The now 58 year old patient was diagnosed diabetic four years prior, the diagnosis being changed to Type 1 following a positive autoantibody test. The patient had not used insulin, but has been on low dose Metformin (500 mg once daily), relying primarily on diet (very low carbohydrate at <50 g/day) and exercise interventions for glycemic control, HbA_{1c} tests routinely returning results less than 45 mmol/mol.²³ Here, we describe the glycemic effect, following introduction of Dapagliflozin (5mg/day) with continued blood glucose monitoring during and after withdrawal of Dapagliflozin.

Self-monitoring of blood glucose concentration was conducted every 2nd or 3rd day (CareSens N finger prick testing). A testing day began with a 6:30 a.m. (\pm 15 minutes) fasting test, with the rest being pre and 2 hour post meals.

Results and Discussion

Background glucose concentrations had a fairly long period of monitoring indicating an elevated glycaemia, but generally within the range of 9 ± 3 mmol/L.²³ The fasting test is typically the highest of the day, confirming both the low carbohydrate diet (no meal-associated spikes in glucose) and therefore blood glucose is derived from gluconeogenesis. This hyperglycaemia is likely resulting from hyperglucagonemia without adequate glycemic management from insulin.^{33,34} In addition, the evening test (6:00 p.m. \pm 30 minutes) shows a much reduced hyperglycaemia. Of particular interest is the difference Dapagliflozin treatment has on these measures, notably a marked drop in the fasting tests but very much reduced effect in the evening measures (Figure 1).

During Dapagliflozin treatment, any time glucose measures generally dropped to the range 8 ± 3 mmol/L, a reduction of 1-1.5 mmol/L. This is consistent with clinical trials of this drug.^{9,10,15,16,19,38}

The effect of inhibition of SGLT2 was rapidly reversed on cessation of Dapagliflozin treatment, but the stimulation of glucagon and resulting hyperglycaemia appears to be of a longer term nature (Figure 1). Unfortunately, whether the peak post-treatment fasting hyperglycaemia (>14 mmol/L) would resolve naturally or not cannot be determined as the patient began Glipizide and subsequently insulin therapy.

Dyslipidaemia is apparent within a short period of commencing treatment (Table 1). This resolved quickly on ceasing treatment. A modified serum lipid profile has been noted previously, especially LDL-C.^{3,14,19} Stimulation of endogenous glucose release, reported for Dapagliflozin, in a very low carbohydrate diet requires gluconeogenesis from lipid resources. The presence of elevated serum lipids is therefore unsurprising, firstly in a ketogenic state^{25,37} and especially with additional intensive athletic activity.⁶ Artificially elevated serum lipids induce raised glucagon concentration.²⁸ These therefore suggest a possible indirect link between Dapagliflozin action, via elevated serum lipids and raised glucagon, to increased glucose production.

Figure 1 Fasting and early evening blood glucose tests (mmol/L) covering the period including the Dapagliflozin use plus some months on either side. Typically the fasting (circles) and evening (triangles) cover the highest and lowest glucose tests within a day. The Dapagliflozin start and stop dates are marked by vertical lines.

The triglyceride/HDL ratio is suggested to be a good proxy for insulin resistance, with >3.5 indicating resistance.²⁰ Insulin resistance is a common marker of type 2 diabetes, thus induced insulin resistance suggested by this result could indicate SGLT2-inhibition, while reducing serum glucose concentration, might exacerbate existing insulin resistance, although Dapagliflozin has also been reported to reduce muscular insulin resistance.²¹ This ratio resolved rapidly on ceasing medication (Table 1).

Table 1 Serum lipids panel (mmol/L). Note marked change in both total cholesterol and triglycerides within a few weeks of starting Dapagliflozin medication, as well as the triglycerides/HDL ratio.

	Total Cholesterol	Triglycerides	HDL	LDL	Ch/HDL	Trig/HDL
December 2016	4.9	1.9	0.98	3.1	5	1.9
December 2017	6.1	3.6	0.86	3.6	7.1	4.2
March 2018	4.7	1.6	1.06	2.9	4.4	1.5
September 2018	5.2	2.2	0.94	3.3	5.5	2.3

Dapagliflozin has been demonstrated to stimulate glucagon with subsequent endogenous glucose release. From these results, it may be inferred that this effect remains for quite some time after treatment ceases, as indicated by the increased overnight fasted serum glucose concentration. This has been suggested to be specifically linked to SGLT2 activity in the pancreas,² although neither α - nor β -cells are reported to exhibit SGLT2 activity,^{5,29-31} therefore there must also be doubt that SGLT2 inhibition in pancreatic α -cells is the mechanism or source of Dapagliflozin-induced glucagon. SGLT inhibition clearly has an effect on processes beyond glucose recovery from the urine volume.

Lifestyle effects were noted. Specifically, polyuria disturbed sleep at 4-6 occasions per night. Further, intestinal discomfort and loose bowels, 5-6 on the Bristol stool chart,¹⁸ may have contributed to initial weight loss. This was unexpected as gliflozins are extremely selective for SGLT2 rather than SGLT1 inhibition, although they may easily provide some inhibition for intestinal SGLT1 at common oral dosages.⁸ Reduced uptake of glucose from the intestinal lumen readily induces diarrhoea, with a complete absence of SGLT1 resulting in glucose/galactose malabsorption.³⁹ SGLT inhibition is known to raise glucagon concentration,^{27,30} α -cells are known to express SGLT1 transporters² and also exist in the gastrointestinal system.³² This therefore raises the possibility that raised glucagon production

may be gastrointestinal rather than pancreatic in origin, although recent evidence indicates hyperglucagonemia associated with hyperglycaemia is reversed under SGLT1 inhibition.¹⁷ The concentration of Dapagliflozin at the intestinal lining is presumably sufficient to inhibit glucose uptake to produce a mild glucose-induced diarrhoea, but inadequate inhibition to prevent excess glucagon production under hyperglycaemic conditions.

Conclusion

Dapagliflozin treatment produced the expected improvement in glycemic control, but without resolving to normoglycaemia. The expected polyuria with polydipsia occurred. Some lipid profile disturbance may be expected and is reported here. Not previously reported are the intestinal effects.

The broader effects of SGLT2 inhibition on both glucose concentration resulting in glucosuria and glucagon stimulation (gastrointestinal and/or pancreatic) reported here are of possible concern for long term use of this treatment.

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